
ECO-INNOVATION DEVELOPMENT OF ENTERPRISES IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of the development of eco-innovations in the hospitality industry. It is proved that the greening of production activities at hospitality industry enterprises will not only contribute to improving the quality of life of the population, effective integration into the local regional ecosystem, but also serve as a source of competitive advantage.

It is substantiated that in order to restore and build the economy of the future and integrate into the global political, economic and business community, Ukraine must already comply with the requirements of the «green economy», innovation, transparency and responsibility of business, and reduce the negative impact on the environment and society.

It is determined that the defining concept of greening the economy is the transition to an energy-efficient, resource-saving, innovative and socially inclusive development model based on an optimal balance between natural physical, and human capital, and involves the use of innovations, changing the value creation cycle through the use of digital technologies.

Keywords: hospitality industry, eco-innovations, hotel industry, restaurant industry, greening of hospitality enterprises, eco-trends.

Statement of the problem. The eco-innovative development of hospitality industry enterprises is the most popular direction for effective functioning at the present stage of management. After all, eco-innovations serve as a means of ensuring the efficient use of natural resources, reducing the environmental burden on the environment and a lever for the use of additional sources of value creation.

The introduction of environmental «green» innovations in accommodation and catering facilities helps to increase their competitiveness in the tourism market and demonstrates the existence of a socially responsible economic and production policy as part of a hotel or restaurant brand, which is an important factor in shaping consumer choice for the modern generation. In addition, the greening of production activities in the hospitality sector will not only contribute to improving the quality of life of the population, effective integration into the local regional ecosystem, but also serves as a source of competitive advantages for hotel and restaurant enterprises, which is extremely important in today's environment of instability.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Many foreign and domestic scientists have studied the development and implementation of innovations and eco-innovations. In particular, I. Ansoff, J. K. Galbraith, K. Oppenlander, B. Santo, P. Drucker, J. Schumpeter, N. Andreeva, I. Bystriakov, O. Veklych,

V. Dzhindzhoyan, I. Sokyrnyk, I. Oshchypok, and many others.

However, further research is needed on the issues of effective and rational implementation of eco-innovations in the hospitality industry, which will be aimed at the economic growth of Ukraine, because today in Ukraine there is an increase in environmental threats, while the threats are systemic and should be considered, first of all, as a threat to national security in the environmental sphere.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. To date not enough attention has been paid to the study of the development of eco-innovations in the hospitality industry during crises caused by various situations, including pandemics, war, etc.

Formulation of the objectives of the article (statement of the task). The purpose of the article is to theoretically substantiate the main tools for introducing eco-innovations in the hospitality industry and their special role in providing a win-win solution to improve competitiveness, business sustainability and sustainable development of the country.

Summary of the main research material. According to certain approaches, eco-innovations serve as a means of ensuring the efficient use of natural resources, reducing the environmental burden on the environment and a lever for engaging additional sources of value creation, increasing business competitiveness,

and expanding productive employment. They provide win-win solutions for improving economic competitiveness and business sustainability, as they start at the level of business entities' strategy and have an impact beyond them in the supply chain and value chain.

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in Europe defines eco-innovation «as the creation or introduction of new or significantly improved products (goods and services), processes, methods marketing methods, organizational structures and institutional arrangements that - with or without intentionally or unintentionally - lead to an improvement of the environment compared to relevant alternatives» [8].

The European Commission defines eco-innovation as any form of innovation that aims at or results in significant and demonstrable progress towards achieving sustainable development goals by reducing environmental impact, increasing resilience to environmental stress, or achieving more efficient and responsible use of natural resources [2].

The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) defines eco-innovations from the standpoint business, namely:... «is the development and application of a business model formed a new business strategy that incorporates sustainability into all business transactions that based on life cycle thinking and collaboration with partners value chain»[5].

With certain approaches, eco-innovations serve as a means of ensuring efficient use of natural resources, reduction of ecological environmental load and lever for use of additional sources value creation, business competitiveness enhancement, expansion productive employment.

Eco-innovations lead to complex solutions aimed at reducing expenditure of resources and energy, while

improving the quality of products and services. However, in terms of load characteristics, they can to change quite significantly.

This is best reflected in the expected results impact of eco-innovations on the economy, natural environment, society and stages of value addition in global value chains.

Attracting eco-innovations increases the level of greening of business, which carries one of the main goals of the concept of sustainable development. Achieving mass implementation of environmentally oriented innovations requires real sources of funding.

So, for Ukraine to enter the sustainable path of economic development, it is necessary to critically analyze the backlog of policy gaps and clearly identify the activators of the movement towards the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

One of the activators of the movement towards the SDGs is also the development of hotel and restaurant business. After all, we all know that the enterprises of the hospitality industry, namely the hotel and restaurant industries, are colossal consumers of energy and water on a global scale, and their impact on the environment is hidden due to the fact that it is usually perceived as a separate sector of the service sector, and not as interrelated components of a single complex, the main task of which is to meet the ever-growing needs of tourists.

In new tourist regions, projects are often implemented for the construction of large hotel and restaurant complexes that produce waste and pollution in volumes that local communities cannot cope with. Excessive consumption of energy, water, fuel by tourists often takes these resources from the local population (Table 1).

Table 1.

The main causes and consequences of the negative impact of the hotel and restaurant sector and tourism on the environment

Type of impact	Sources of pollution	Environmental impact
Water use	Household drains	Water pollution, reduction of water resources
Energy use	Imperfect heating systems	Air pollution, climate imbalance
Use of soils	Excessive building, trampling, unorganized rest near accommodation and catering	Changes in soil structure, increase in their density, soil degradation
Using the aesthetic value of landscapes	Spontaneous development of an overnight base in the private sector	Visual contamination, deterioration of aesthetic value
Clogging of the area around the accommodation and food facilities	Excessive number of visitors	Threat to living and inanimate nature

Therefore, today the greening of enterprises of the hospitality industry plays a key role in ensuring the sustainable development of the economy of the country and the region.

The essence of greening is to minimize the negative impact of tourism on the environment due to the consumption of a significant amount of traditional energy resources. In accordance with the concepts of sustainable development, it is worth highlighting the basic

principles on the basis of which environmental activities in the hotel and restaurant business should be based:

1. Minimal environmental impact. Conservation and sustainable use of natural, social and cultural resources.
2. Minimal influence and respect for local cultures.
3. Increase of economic advantages and assistance for balanced economic development of the area.
4. Increased benefits for tourists.

5. Increasing environmental awareness in the population [4].

The greening of the hotel and restaurant business should concern absolutely all its spheres of activity. Today, the concept of so-called ecological hotels and restaurants is extremely popular in the world. Such institutions try to preserve the health of guests, rationally use natural resources and position themselves as responsible for the impact of the enterprise on the environment.

Leading experts in the hospitality industry note that, in accordance with global trends, preference will be given to environmental trends. Although now many of the world's famous hotel and restaurant chains have their own specialist in ecology.

Environmental issues are prominent in the activities of the International Hotel Association (IHA). Within the framework of the IGA, the IHEI Foundation (International Hotel Environmental Initiative) has been created, the main task of which is to collect and disseminate information on environmental issues related to the hotel industry.

The Foundation has prepared textbooks and CDs, training seminars on ecology are organized in the tourism industry, as well as annual competitions for the best management methods that are developed and used by the hotel and restaurant sector in order to improve the environmental situation.

Eleven major international hotel chains included in the fund have already saved significant funds as a result of the measures taken. For example, InterContinental has saved £10 million over the past 10 years, installed furniture and accessories from biological materials in rooms that can be recycled and used again.

In developed countries, the concept of an ecological hotel was formed, which is a qualitatively thought-out system of comfortable life in harmony with the outside world. It is a system of conceptually new view in the development of accommodation facilities, which allows both to take care of nature and significantly reduce production costs. Despite the fact that the concept is at the stage of formation, it is already possible to distinguish a number of features of an ecological hotel.

First of all, it is a well-thought-out system of resource and energy saving, including strict standards of resource saving and widespread use of alternative energy sources. This feature is primarily associated with the insufficient resource availability of developed countries and active policies aimed at stimulating energy conservation. Many hotels use solar energy both direct heating of water and obtaining electric energy. Studies have shown that thanks to the use of new environmental methods of work (for example, solar heating of water) and small investments in hotels and restaurants, it is possible to reduce electricity consumption by 10-25%, and water consumption by 30%.

«Green» hotels try to minimize chemicals, especially hard to clean. In cleaning and sewerage systems, priority is given to advanced methods using bacteria that decompose dirt and waste. In cleaning agents, chlorine-containing compounds are limited as allergenic and adversely affecting the environment. Detergents and washing powders are also chosen «most spared»,

but, of course, they can provide a «hotel» cleanliness class.

Competent disposal is one of the main priorities. Solid waste should not enter the surrounding nature, so the garbage is sorted, pressed and removed. Liquid waste is either placed in special containers and taken out, or cleaned. The most advanced eco-hotels are moving towards attempts to build completely closed systems where water and air could be regenerated, which would allow the construction of such hotels within specially protected natural areas.

Most eco-hotels are located in unique natural complexes - on the shores of the cleanest lakes, rivers, in reserves and protected areas. This, on the one hand, is due to the fact that such places attract people who care about the fate of nature. and, on the other hand, such a complex minimally harms the surrounding nature, which allows it to be preserved in pristine beauty. The construction of an ordinary non-ecological hotel is limited by the requirements for the preservation of the natural environment and is often prohibited.

High requirements in such hotels impose and catering. Most eco-hotels try to use organic food of organic standards. In the simplest case, these are environmentally friendly products of local manufacturers, in more advanced products that have passed special strict control of European or American certification organizations. Water quality is also important. A real hotel in the ideology of «eco» should carefully monitor the composition of the water it uses.

There are no special requirements for the internal design of such hotels, but they are usually made in natural materials and shades. The main colors are white, earth colors, green, gray, often red and orange are used as additional.

Bed linen uses pure cotton grown without the use of pesticides and herbicides. Another ultra-modern trend is the use of recycled materials in the design.

Many eco-friendly hotels in connection with energy savings, refuse computers and televisions. This is not only savings, but above all an attempt to distract guests from the hustle and bustle and bring them closer to a peaceful and relaxing holiday in the bosom of nature.

As for the enterprises of the restaurant industry, the ecological style fits perfectly into the restaurant in rooms of different shapes and sizes. It perfectly emphasizes any concepts - from healthy eating to sophisticated seafood dishes. This design allows you to create the most comfortable and very stylish atmosphere. It's nice to eat, relax, communicate.

In the restaurant space, eco-design has the following features:

1. The use of a large number of natural materials. Various breeds of natural wood, various types of stone, ceramics, etc. are actively used in eco-style. You can also attract materials created from recycled materials.

2. The color scheme is natural and calm. In such restaurants there are no acid-bright details. The main colors of the ecological style are different shades of brown, gray, natural green, blue. In general, everything that can be found in wildlife is suitable. But it is necessary to observe the measure.

3. Landscaping as the main decoration. Living plants in eco-style are an obligatory part of the interior. In restaurants it can be plants in pots, house trees, vertical gardening and even open green terraces. You can complement the picture with small flowers on each table.

4. Nice soft lighting. Ecological style does not withstand bright white all-encompassing light. Its option is soft yellow or natural light. Original lamps and sconces are used as lighting tools.

Modern technology also fits perfectly into the concept of eco. All energy-saving technologies become the decoration of the restaurant in this style. It is also allowed to combine features from other styles - loft, modernism, etc.

Thus, the main difference between eco-hotel and eco-restaurant is the ideology of proximity of man and nature, which is built on this basis, it is a complex system of measures aimed at reducing the impact of anthropogenic activity on the environment.

In accordance with international standards, the environmental impact of collective accommodation and catering facilities is assessed in the following areas:

1. Air: smell (production and consumption of electricity and heat, cooking, transport used by tourists and staff).

2. Water: water supply, water consumption (in the kitchen, when cleaning, in the sauna, rooms, when providing tourist services).

3. Soil and groundwater: protection of groundwater (in the provision of tourism services, waste disposal).

4. Noise: composition and noise level (in the place of rest, in the provision of tourist services).

5. Visual actions: territory; the surrounding area; landscape; buildings; marketing; waste; travel services.

6. Food and its quality.

The basis for creating an «ecological» hotel is the desire to make the most of natural resources and natural materials in order not to pollute the atmosphere.

Compliance of hotels with the requirements is confirmed by certification and assignment of certain characters. In 1991 The International Association for Standardization (ISO) has created the environmental management standard ISO 14001 (EMS).

In order to comply with it, the organization is obliged to confirm that it has a special environmental policy. The ISO 14001 standard is the minimum that every enterprise must adhere to in order to negate the harm to the environment. In a number of countries, in addition to ISO 14001, their own standards were created, for example, in the UK - BS 7750 Specification for Environmental Management Systems, in Canada - CAN/CSA Z750-94: Guidelines for an Environmental Management System, in European Union - EMAS.

For certification of eco-hotels there is also an authoritative system «Leadership in energy and environmental design». Only environmentally friendly buildings can receive LEED certification. The objective, well-known worldwide LEED rating relies on energy and water savings, as well as environmentally friendly raw materials. LEED - energy saving and environmental protection system using solar panels.

There are a number of organizations in the world that are engaged in the development and implementation of environmental management systems.

British Airways Holidays (BAH) is one of the largest air carriers and tour operators in the world. The company regularly monitors hotels in the Caribbean and provides all possible assistance to accommodation facilities with good environmental management. In addition, its employees observe how this management technology is suitable for the hotel industry. The work of the VAN related to the preparation of criteria for eco-management was the first attempt to create requirements common to all hotels so that the traveler could immediately understand the level of service and quality of services he could expect.

Certification for Sustainable Tourism (CST) is one of the leading and most successful ecotourism companies in the western hemisphere. She managed to create her own market by developing a state program of environmental management and its active dissemination. Despite the fact that it is focused on the tourism industry as a whole, mainly hotels are certified. In order to obtain an eco-quality mark, the hotel must minimize its environmental damage, and experts assess the socio-economic effect of the enterprise's work in a particular region, conduct interviews with guests and management. Each criterion defines a set of actions, and the system as a whole turns out to be comprehensive.

Green Globe is a British company that actively promotes and implements ecotourism, operates in more than 50 countries, a full member of the UN Tourism Organization and the World Tourism and Travel Council. The criteria for obtaining certification include basic standard requirements for reducing waste, saving electricity, introducing an environmental management system, social and cultural development, reducing risks, assessing the relationship between the geographical location of a hotel or resort and its impact on the environment.

Green Key (Denmark) develops certification programs for catering services of hotels, hostels, congress centers, rest houses. Eco-labeling of this company was awarded to 2700 hotels and other institutions in 56 countries. Before receiving the eco-sign, the company must establish standards for water consumption and saving, introduce a system for reusing resources, and begin to purchase environmentally friendly organic products.

Strict requirements are put forward for nutrition. The menu should have at least two organic products, at least one low-fat snack and one low-fat main dish. In addition, there are criteria for lighting, ventilation, work with the disabled, irrigation systems, garbage collection. The organisation now has 97 members, including the Radisson SAS network.

Touristik Union International (TUI) - leading tour operator in Germany with more than five million customer base, one of the first in the country began to promote the principles of environmental responsibility in the tourism industry. Among its members are more than 7,000 hotels worldwide.

BREEAM (Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method) or «Environmental

Performance Assessment Method from the Building Research Institute», UK). BREEAM was the first standard for assessing the environmental friendliness of real estate.

The international ISO standard is 14001 quite strict, now a number of hotels in Western Europe are certified - in Germany, Portugal and Sweden, in particular, Forum Hotels, Intercontinental Hotels, Lusotur Golfes, Renaissance, Sanga Saby Kurs, Konference Cur enter, and in Southeast Asia (Hong Kong and Mauritius) it is Island Shangrila-La Hotel, Kowloon Shangrila-La Hotel, Labourdonnais Waterfront Hotel [12].

Ukrainian enterprises are just beginning to chase the ecological future and every day face a lot of obstacles: difficulties in legislation, high prices for imported green technologies, lack of mass sorting and corresponding waste processing plants. Of course, the situation is improving every year, more and more people and enterprises are beginning to take care of the state of the ecosystem, so it is very important to catch up every day and break down stereotypical thinking. Therefore, after analyzing the state of affairs in the hotel and restaurant industry, it is possible to determine the TOP of world eco-initiatives that Ukrainian hospitality industry enterprises can use today.

1. Solid waste recycling.

Incredibly, but true - sorting is the first step towards sustainability. In developed countries, this is already a normal practice not only in enterprises, but also in everyday life. The answer is that there are not enough enterprises in Ukraine where it is possible to recycle paper, plastic, glass, etc. However, the more high-quality sorted material, the sooner the corresponding enterprises appear that will not only take care of the environment, but also bring profit to the owners.

It is worth recalling shocking figures - ordinary office paper decomposes within two years, cans -10 years, foil and batteries - more than 100 years, plastic bottles - 180-200 years, aluminum cans - 500 years and glass for 1000 years. These figures are already a good reason for sorting, and hotels and restaurants as large complexes, through which thousands of people pass every year, have great leverage. Among the trending initiatives, we can note the replacement of plastic key cards from the numbers with paper and wooden counterparts, which in fact are not only «green», but also aesthetically pleasing.

2. Ecological cosmetic and chemical products. Many hotels in Ukraine equip rooms with cosmetics, and also use many chemicals for cleaning and washing clothes. Therefore, hotels have the right to choose high-quality eco-friendly cosmetic products for their guests. There are many brands that do not use sulfates, which not only pollute water, but also adversely affect the skin of people. Ideally, you should also pay attention to whether the products are tested on animals. To reduce the use of washing powders and water, many hotels in Ukraine already put information cards so that guests themselves regulate the need to change bed linen and towels. In this properly constructed communication with the guest is the real key to success.

3. Responsible attitude to the quality of food and its appropriate disposal. One element of sustainability

is the support of local brands, which in the hotel and restaurant industry is reflected in collaboration with food and drink suppliers. In general, the food industry in Ukraine is developed and you can buy almost any product locally, except for certain delicacies (red and black caviar, seafood, some varieties of meat). But at this point it is worth emphasizing the correct disposal. Composting is not common in Ukraine, but in hotels and restaurants it is one of the best investments in the processing of organic waste. Compost tanks exist in different sizes, are sealed and provide processing of organic garbage of plant and animal origin. Also, together with organic matter, paper napkins can be recycled. The cost in Ukraine - from 2000 hryvnia and above, depending on the manufacturer and size.

4. Energy-saving technologies. They are also publicly available in Ukraine, so their implementation is quite acceptable. First, the automatic switching on of light in the premises not only reduces the electricity bill, but also is a manifestation of the careful use of resources. Also, the installation of solar panels, especially in the southern regions of the country, has long been an economically justified investment.

5. Attitude of guests to eco-initiatives. Without the support of guests, any enterprise of the hospitality industry will never be 100% environmentally friendly. Communication and interaction of staff is a key point in the work of any hotel. Nowadays, there is a widespread practice of «paperless guest» in the world - reducing the use of paper per guest by introducing electronic signatures on registration cards, sending invoices to e-mail instead of a printed copy and providing all the necessary information through mobile applications, sites and e-mail.

The attitude of guests to food consumption is changing - at the all-inclusive resorts they actively promote taking as much food as you can really eat. No, not because it's a pity or the hotel wants to save, it's just hard to imagine how much waste remains after the hotel for 200 rooms, working on a buffet system. Sometimes this figure reaches 500 kg of organic waste per day. In addition, hotels come up with new features with the provision of clean water to guests - coolers on the floors, glass bottles that are filled again, etc. The main thing is to have creativity and meet the requirements of your customers.

Thus, the inclusion of environmental aspects in the development of hotel and restaurant services is simultaneously associated with several trends. On the one hand, there is an increase in customer demand for service. This is manifested because the level of education has increased significantly, and tourists every year more and more enrich their knowledge about the environment, care, which has become a fashion trend.

The results of numerous studies and surveys have shown that residents of developed countries tend to prefer hotels that care about the environment and natural resources. Moreover, 70% of tourists are willing to pay \$150 more for a two-week stay in a hotel where environmental standards are observed.

On the other hand, entrepreneurs are aware that environmental issues can provide a competitive ad-

vantage over the service market. The introduction of resource-saving technologies will reduce costs and, accordingly, increase the profit of enterprises.

The emergence of new accommodation facilities significantly increases the attractiveness of the tourist destination and increases the flow of tourists. The quality of service and additional services when placing depend on such aspects of tourism as a high score of the organization of recreation and leisure of tourists in a particular country, as well as overall satisfaction with the journey.

In Ukraine, there is a demand for ecological means of accommodation and maintenance, but there are different visions in the definitions of the concept of «collective means of placement of an ecological orientation». This is due to the lack of regulatory documents in this area. It is necessary to develop recommendations for improving the work of hotel and restaurant enterprises taking into account environmental factors and stimulate their implementation in practice.

The trend for environmental friendliness is one of the most popular today, and it penetrates deeper into all spheres of human life. Residents of cities learn to use less plastic, practice the principles of zero waste, without producing new garbage, using things again, practice the principle of ugly fruits, the trend to buy vegetables and fruits of different shapes, or even not by kilograms, but by the piece. Many, and not for vegetarian reasons, refuse products of animal origin, milk, meat, fish in favor of plant analogues based on various types of legumes, chickpeas, as well as other products of coconut, almond, soy and oat milk.

Among entrepreneurs, ecotrends are also becoming popular, as among city dwellers. The goals are common: firstly, to reduce the amount of waste, secondly, to use resources more efficiently, thirdly, to reduce the amount of plastic and its derivatives, and fourth, to follow the trend.

Also in the restaurant business rationally relate to the use of animal products, especially meat products. «Noise to tail» (using the entire carcass of the animal along with the insides, and not just a few fillet parts). In the Chicken Kyiv restaurant, most dishes are prepared from chicken, rationally using different parts for different dishes.

An equally popular trend is local food (local foods and -Delo.ua components), which means dishes prepared on the basis of local components - vegetables, fruits, fish and meat grown or caught within the same country.

The same applies to alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages, the trend is to use local wine, beer, juices and other local products. This trend is due to the fact that less human resources, time, fuel are spent on the cultivation, production, delivery of these goods than on the delivery of goods from other countries or continents.

Now in fashion reusable dishes, its own containers, biodegradable tubes for drinks, as an alternative to plastic. All this is the response of restaurateurs to customer requests.

So many entrepreneurs offer a discount for a drink of about 10% when it is poured into the visitor's container. When it comes to disposable dishes, restaurateurs prefer containers made from recyclable materials.

Some establishments even serve dishes in edible dishes. According to this principle, the restaurant «Villa Alfold» in Uzhgorod works. Although to be quite precise, the idea itself is not new - back in the 90s, some Kyiv restaurants offered visitors borsch in a loaf of bread.

Increasingly, there are analogues to plastic tubes made of paper or other materials.

Another ecotrend, a proposal to sort garbage in fast food establishments. For example, in Lviv at Bubble Waffle, guests are offered to sort garbage for paper or plastic waste on their own. Thus, the institution not only pays attention to the problem of garbage, but also stimulates guests to think about this at home.

Towards recovery and building the economy of the future, integration into world political, economic and business community Ukraine already has comply with the requirements of the «green economy», innovation, transparency and business responsibility, reducing the negative impact on the environment and society etc.

The defining concept of greening the economy is the transition to energy-efficient, resource-saving, innovative and socially inclusive development model based on the optimal balance between natural, physical and human capital, and involves the use of innovation (information and communication, technological, environmental, social, etc.) and changing the value cycle through the application of digital technologies.

Modern business in the hospitality industry needs innovative ideas that can withstand the latest challenges of mankind (climate change; environmental pollution; exhaustion of valuable natural resources; degradation of ecosystems, etc.), and creates favorable conditions for entrepreneurs who are ready to produce new value through the implementation of eco-innovations. Now for business it is not enough to use environmental approaches only to develop a new product or reduction of production costs. It is also necessary to apply the latest methods and tools to win the prestige and trust of society.

The economic development of the country should ideally be accompanied by sustainable use of natural resources and waste management, support for biodiversity, conservation of natural ecosystems and economic use of natural resource potential. In these circumstances, state policy should be aimed at creating conditions for increasing the competitiveness of the national economy on the basis of eco-innovations as the basis of dynamic development and reducing significant imbalances between them in productivity and living standards.

Scaling of environmental innovations is not only a modern trend of innovation and investment stage for sustainable development of European countries, which requires an increased sense of environmental awareness of each subject of the market and normalized load on the environment. This is a necessary impetus to create conditions for effective stabilization of the level of development of the EU countries and Ukraine.

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